

Cryopreservation of Natural Killer cells in droplets

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ABSTRACT

Current Natural Killer (NK) cryopreservation protocols lead to loss of NK cell viability and functionality (1,2), highlighting the need for more efficient protocols. 3D cryopreservation enhances the post-thaw viability and functionality as compared with cell suspension and monolayer culture methods (2). To our knowledge, there is no attempt to preserve NK cells using droplet-based microfluidics. We have applied our Microniche platform (3) to generate 3D NK cell laden alginate droplets with improved cell protection. Our preliminary data reveals high viability of cryopreserved NK cells in single-layer beads using DMSO in FBS, opening new possibilities towards NK cell cryopreservation with minimum cell loss and damage during freeze-thawing process.

KEYWORDS: Cryopreservation, Natural Killer cells, biomicrofluidics, microdroplets

INTRODUCTION

Conventional 2D NK cryopreservation protocols use dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) as cryoprotectant and a slow-freezing method causing deterioration in NK cell viability and functionality (1,2). Despite the significant advances in maintaining viability and functionality using microfluidics for cell cryopreservation, no attempt has been described using NK cells. Advantages of cell cryopreservation by microfluidics include the recapitulation of the 3D cellular environment and the protective role of the hydrogel layer. Our Microniche technology (3) was adapted to generate single layer beads. This system would protect the embedded cells from mechanical and osmotic stress during the freeze-thawing process allowing the bidirectional diffusion of nutrients, oxygen and waste products.

EXPERIMENTAL

The device operational is described in Figure 1. The microfluidic platform was manufactured in Polymethyl methacrylate (PMMA) and designed using Solidworks CAD software (3). Microdroplets were generated by hydrodynamic focusing and flows driven by gravity means. Droplets traveled through a meandering channel containing two laminar mineral oil flows, one containing acetic acid. Calcium ions were released by the diffusion of the acetic acid across the oil interface leading to droplet gelation. Flows were adjusted to generate 400 μm diameter droplets. Alginate 1,5% w.t. containing calcium carbonate nanopowder 1,5% w.t. was used as a sample. NK cells from healthy donors were isolated using standard procedures and added to the hydrogel sample to a concentration of 5×10^6 cells/ml. Beads were generated, collected and washed in PBS three times. Then, they were transferred into cryovials (Corning) containing FBS 10% DMSO and cooled down to -180°C using Corning cool cell LX freezing system for 24 h; afterwards vials were transferred to liquid nitrogen tanks at -180°C for storage and after 2 weeks vials were warmed up to ambient temperature, washed, transferred to their culture media and cultured for a week. After collection, all generated beads were visualized and analyzed under confocal imaging. For this purpose, FITC-CD34+ DAPI assay (3) was performed to assess viability and expansion of the enclosed NK cells. Images before and after cryopreservation were taken at 24h, 48h, 72h, and 1 week (Figure 2).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

NK cells in single alginate beads were successfully produced, cryopreserved in FBS +10% DMSO and cultured for up to a week. Images were analyzed using ImageJ software to assess NK cell viability and expansion. It was shown an approximately post-thaw viability of 95% after 24 h, decreasing slightly until approximately 82% at week 1. Additionally the average number of NK cells per droplet increased significantly during the first week, from an average of 78 cells/droplet to 160 cells/droplet at week 1 (Figure 2), suggesting this method also favors NK cell expansion. We believe the passive and “soft” bead generation method used, together with the added protection of the hydrogel layer and the 3D cell structure recapitulation provide an efficient tool for NK cryopreservation.

Figure 1: a) Adapted Microniche technology schematic b) CAD microdevice design- single layer droplet c) NK bead model

Figure 2: a) 3D post-thaw NK cell laden culture images in three different Z planes b) Left: Post-thaw empty bead 24 h. Right: Schematic of three imaging Z planes: c) Detail 1 week post-thaw NK cell laden bead d) Post-thaw NK cell survival percentage (N=3)(1 week) e) Post-thaw average NK cell number per droplet (N=3)(1 week)

CONCLUSION

We have successfully generated NK cell laden beads able to be used as cryopreservation vehicles, maintaining bead stability and a high cell viability after a week. To our knowledge this is the first attempt to cryopreserve NK cells in droplets. This promising preliminary results could be improved by adjusting the hydrogel type and composition, cryoprotectant type and cryopreservation media, and therefore lead to an optimum cryopreservation method for NK cells with minimum cell damage, degradation, and cell loss during freeze–thawing process.

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